

SOCIO-ECONOMIC SITUATION, PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS IN KASHKADARYA REGION IN 1986-1989

Nurbek Suyarov

doctorant student of QarDu

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Abstract. This article presents the socio-economic situation, problems and solutions in the Kashkadarya region in 1986-1989 (which was part of the Uzbek SSR).

Key words. Soviet power, repression, "Cotton case", detention center, Communist Party, "reconstruction", recession, T.Gdlyan, N.Ivanov, cotton dictatorship.

The plenum of the Central Committee of the Communist Party was convened in April 1985, and the program called "reconstruction" of Soviet society was adopted. This program put on the agenda the issue of deep reform of all spheres of life of the socialist society, including the economic, socio-political and spiritual-cultural spheres. The main task of the "Reconstruction" program was to democratize the social life of peoples living under the socialist system, to introduce the principle of transparency in political life, and to accelerate economic development based on scientific and technical achievements. No matter how much efforts were made to implement the "Reconstruction" policy by the leadership of the Central State Apparatus, it did not bring the expected results. Moreover, mistakes in the process of using force in the foreign policy of the 80s of the 20th century began to indicate the destruction of the Soviet system. The events taking place in the Kashkadarya region, located in the south of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the actions carried out on the basis of the "Cotton Work" campaign, were causing the residents of this region to strongly protest.

In 1986, the socio-economic situation of Kashkadarya became worse than in 1985. The process of "Cotton case" and "Uzbeks' case" became more intense, and arrests of leaders and expulsion from the party increased. This situation had a negative impact on the implementation of the 1986 plans. Production of low-quality products continued in factories and factories. 22 out of 75 industrial enterprises in Kashkadarya region did not fulfill their production plans this year. In addition, 136 out of 143 existing agricultural farms, almost 82% of cotton farms are mired in backwardness and indebtedness, and the yield per hectare in the region is 14 centners. 50,000 hectares of land were overgrown with reeds, and 60,000 hectares of land were highly saline. About 900 leaders in

Kashkadarya region have been replaced. A number of secretaries of the district and city party committees, chairmen of the executive committee, heads of farms, as well as many responsible persons who were recently recommended for work and have just started work, were relieved of their duties. But these changes did not affect the improvement of the existing situation. During this period, natural gas was not available in 150 villages, stores in 28 villages, and household service enterprises in 327 villages. Especially in Dehkanabad, Qamashi, Yakkabog and other regions, the living standards of the villagers were extremely low. Only in the U. Yusupov district "Sulaymon Murodov" state farm, due to the fault of the "Karshikhurilish" administration, the water pipeline, asphalt road, winter club were not built, only 16 of the 80 cotton-growing brigades in the state farm had field sheds. 36,000 soums allocated in 1985 in the field of natural gas supply by PMK-4 construction organization of the region in Guzor region remained unutilized. In 1986, 45-50 percent of the population of Guzor was provided with drinking water. The construction of only one water reservoir instead of three in the master plan on the Qamashi-Guzor waterway, which supplies the residents of the district with drinking water, is not on the agenda.

On December 27, 1986, a plenum of the regional party committee was held. The organizational issue was discussed there. Normomin Turopov, the first secretary of the Kashkadarya regional committee, was relieved of his duties, and Islam Abduganievich Karimov, the deputy chairman of the Council of Ministers of Uzbekistan, who works as the chairman of the State Planning Committee, was appointed as the first secretary of the regional party committee. At a time when the socio-economic situation in Kashkadarya region is worsening, people's dissatisfaction with the leadership is increasing, and many families are suffering as a result of the "Cotton case" and "Uzbeks case", at this plenum of the regional committee, the people's office in the region The cases of non-fulfillment of the eleven-month plans of 1986 in all areas of the company, appropriation of capital funds, construction and installation work being ignored by the management were analyzed and a critical attitude was expressed. In 1987, 135 farms in 13 districts of the region engaged in the cultivation of raw cotton. This year, the farmers of Kashkadarya region delivered 374,000 tons of cotton, 58,000 tons of grain, 25,000 tons of meat, and 12,000 tons of milk to the state. For 1 soum spent in agriculture, 75 tyins were earned. In those years, capital spending on the social sphere in Kashkadarya increased by 10%, and funds from organizations and enterprises increased by 15%. Food production increased by 20 percent. Production of meat and meat products per population increased by

15%, vegetable cultivation by 30%, potato products by 38%, potato cultivation by 32%.

Since 1988, some conditions and opportunities have been created for the health care of the population of the region. In particular, the total number of beds in existing hospitals in the region was 17,000. 5565 of these places corresponded to the regional hospital. Along with the increase in the number of beds in existing hospitals, attention was paid to the process of providing them with the necessary equipment. This situation made it possible to make a positive solution to issues related to public health. Positive changes were observed in the field of agriculture. Cotton was planted in 136 collective farms and state farms in Chirakchi, Yakkabog, Qamashi, Guzor, Koson, Kitab, Shahrizabz, Karshi, Mubarak, Usman Yusupov, Ulyanov and Nishon regions. As the productivity of the land decreased due to the monopoly of cotton, measures were developed to increase productivity. Due to the increase of wilt and other diseases in the cotton fields, agrotechnical development was carried out. It is possible to see that the growth of agricultural products in the region for many years has been achieved mainly due to the expansion of cultivated areas and the increase of labor force. According to the instructions of the head of the region, starting from this year, it was shown that it is necessary to pay serious attention to the processes of crop rotation and the formation of a sense of land ownership among farmers. This year, 521 thousand tons of crops were grown by the farmers of Kashkadarya. The yield was on average 22 centners and an increase of 4 centners compared to last year was achieved. At the party conference held on February 27, 1988, it was recognized that there had been growth in all areas of the region. In particular, it was noted that the plan of product sales and labor productivity in the industry was more than fulfilled, the volume of goods increased by 1.5 times on average, and a profit of nearly 400 million soums was obtained. Gross output in the agricultural sector increased by 325 million soums or one and a half times. Collective farms and state farms got rid of debts of more than 80 million soums received from the state. The plan to sell cotton was fulfilled with surplus. Also, the production of food products increased by 20 percent. The amount of funds allocated for the improvement of cities and villages has increased. 35 million soums were spent to provide the population with clean drinking water. 15,000 households were gassed. 15,000 households were gassed. More than 250 kilometers of modern roads and bridges were built. Since this year, positive changes have been made in the socio-economic life of the residents of Kashkadarya Oblast.

By 1989, the work done in the agricultural sector of Kashkadarya region bore fruit. In 1986, 40 million soums were lost in agriculture, and by 1989, 186 million soums were profited. This year, 215 million soums were spent on the social sector alone. Also, dozens of programs for socio-economic development of the region were adopted.

Re-investigation processes on the "Uzbeks case" and "cotton case" have begun. The cases of people who were involved in investigative processes and also sentenced to prison sentences from the territory of the region have been re-examined. As a result of this, the judgments of many innocent people involved in the investigation process were suspended.

In conclusion, in 1986 there were many problems in the socio-economic spheres of Kashkadarya region. Many leading personnel were released from their duties, and most of them were involved in the investigative processes of the "cotton affair". The first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov was appointed the first head of the Kashkadarya region. Measures to improve the socio-economic situation were developed. In the field of agriculture, the melerotiv status of the land has improved and cotton productivity has been increased.

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